

Difficult to be fair. Inequality Aversion to Carbon Taxation

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Abstract

This article examines how people perceive the fairness of carbon taxes when distributional outcomes are unequal. While fairness perceptions are known to be crucial for public support of carbon taxation, the mechanisms underlying it remain insufficiently understood. Using a factorial survey experiment with 770 Swiss citizens, we study how inequality aversion affects fairness perceptions, distinguishing between aversion to self-centred inequality and aversion to inequality in society. We find that fairness perceptions are strongly driven by the former: individuals who anticipate benefiting from a carbon tax are significantly more likely to perceive it as fair. At the same time, perceived fairness declines when individuals find themselves better off than others, indicating an aversion to relative advantage. Being worse off than others also reduces perceived fairness, although less consistently. Concerns about unequal outcomes in society play a more limited role and are politically conditioned: right-leaning respondents view unequal outcomes as less fair, whereas left-leaning respondents accept inequality when it disadvantages high emitters. Importantly, these patterns are largely independent of the specific policy sector in which the tax is applied. These findings show that fairness perceptions are shaped less by abstract redistribution principles than by relational comparisons and ideological interpretation. Carbon

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taxes are therefore more likely to be perceived as fair when distributional outcomes minimise salient disparities in net outcomes and can be credibly justified across the political spectrum.

Keywords: Carbon taxation, Fairness perception, Inequality aversion, Factorial survey experiment, Switzerland

1. Introduction

As the negative effects of climate change become increasingly visible, policymakers and researchers are looking for ways to formulate effective policies to mitigate emissions. Carbon taxes are an efficient instrument in curbing emissions while also creating possibilities to foster environmentally friendly innovation and practices (Sterner, 2012; Rausch and Karplus, 2014; Carl and Fedor, 2016; Carattini et al., 2017). By putting a price on emitting behaviour, they offer a clear and understandable signal for consumption (Schaffer, 2021). However, their political implementation has faced significant challenges (Levi, 2021). While research has shown that a lot of resistance stems from a high saliency of the immediate higher costs versus unclear future benefits (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2018), more recent work established perceived fairness of distributional outcomes to be an important predictor for public acceptability of carbon taxation (Jagers et al., 2021; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019; Bergquist et al., 2022; Douenne and Fabre, 2022). Studies have focused on the central role of redistribution in fostering a more progressive outcome in general and increasing monetary outcomes for individuals (Berry, 2019; Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2018; Beiser-McGrath and Bernauer, 2019). However, empirical findings cast doubt on the effect of redistributions on increasing public acceptability, even when the individual monetary outcome may be positive after redistribution (Mildenberger et al., 2022; Fremstad et al., 2022; Brückmann et al., 2026).

To better understand public acceptability of a tax-and-rebate policy, it is important to first examine how redistributions might affect perceived fairness. This is where we see the main novelty of our work: we aim to explain why carbon taxes are considered to be (un)fair. We understand perceived fairness and political acceptability as closely related, but analytically distinct concepts. Acceptability captures behavioural or attitudinal support for a policy, whereas fairness refers to the normative evaluation of whether its outcomes are perceived to be fair (Dermont et al., 2017; Heyen, 2023; Jagers

31 et al., 2021). In that sense, fairness perception constitutes an evaluative
32 mechanism through which the distributional outcomes of carbon taxes are
33 interpreted before translating into political support or opposition. By ex-
34 plicitly focusing on fairness perceptions, this paper seeks to unpack the un-
35 derlying evaluative logic that precedes acceptability (Bergquist et al., 2022).
36 Understanding this mechanism allows for a more precise analysis of how
37 tax-and-rebate policies generate legitimacy or resistance. Research has fo-
38 cused on how tax revenue redistribution should be designed to align with
39 individual fairness ideals or to achieve a more progressive outcome (Maestre-
40 Andrés et al., 2021; Sommer et al., 2022). These studies follow findings that
41 perceived fairness is individual-specific (Alesina et al., 2012; Fleurbaey and
42 Maniquet, 2008; de Boon et al., 2023) and can, in relation to climate policy,
43 encompass different normative questions on how policies are implemented or
44 how people are unequally exposed to the ills and benefits of a policy (Heyen
45 and Wicki, 2024; Dolšak and Prakash, 2022). However, how and when dis-
46 tributional outcomes from a tax-and-rebate policy themselves are considered
47 (un)fair remains empirically unexplored and often assumed to fall in line with
48 preferences for specific redistributive schemes (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019;
49 Sommer et al., 2022).

50 We empirically test how citizens perceive unequal distributional outcomes
51 of a carbon-tax-and-rebate policy. We base our analysis on the concept of
52 inequality aversion (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999), which has been proposed as a
53 theoretical framework for studying carbon tax acceptability by Sommer et al.
54 (2022). Inequality aversion refers to a respondent’s disutility when unequal
55 outcomes occur. By distinguishing between sociotropic (i.e. unequal out-
56 comes in society) and egotropic (i.e. unequal outcomes relative to one’s own
57 outcome inequality aversion), we extend this theoretical approach (Mansfield
58 and Mutz, 2009). This distinction has been applied to the study of carbon
59 tax acceptability (Beiser-McGrath and Bernauer, 2024), but not to perceived
60 fairness.

61 We conducted a survey in Switzerland, using a representative sample of
62 770 Swiss citizens. The survey included a factorial experiment, in which we
63 showed several vignettes to each respondent (Auspurg and Hinz, 2014). Each
64 vignette included a description of a revenue-neutral carbon tax-and-rebate
65 policy, with hypothetical distributional outcomes for two model households.
66 The distributional outcomes were estimated by varying tax rates, tax ob-
67 jects (heating fuel tax, transport fuel tax, air travel fee), and redistributive
68 schemes (egalitarian, progressive, regressive), while holding total emissions
69 constant (Siegrist et al., 2019). Respondents rated the perceived fairness of
70 the distributional outcomes for each vignette. The difference in outcomes
71 between the model households is used as a measure of sociotropic inequality.
72 To estimate egotropic inequality, we elicited each respondent’s consumption
73 behaviour and estimated their monetary outcome for each vignette. The
74 difference between this estimation and the model’s household outcomes was
75 defined as egotropic inequality.

76 We report several important findings: First, as expected, we find that in-
77 equality aversion significantly reduces perceived fairness. Egotropic inequal-
78 ity aversion reduces fairness perception more consistently than sociotropic in-
79 equality aversion. Having a higher estimated outcome than the model house-
80 holds (advantaged egotropic inequality aversion) has a more robust negative
81 effect than having a lower estimated outcome (disadvantaged inequality aver-
82 sion). Second, the effect of sociotropic inequality aversion is moderated by
83 political orientation: Only right-wing respondents show the expected nega-
84 tive, significant effect, even after controlling for egotropic inequality aversion.
85 Left-wing respondents are even in favour of unequal sociotropic outcomes
86 when inequality is to the detriment of high-emitting households. Third, we
87 do not find significant differences between policy designs. Our respondents
88 judged unequal outcomes similarly, irrespective of whether the carbon tax
89 was levied on heating fuel, transport fuel or air travel fees.

90 Our findings help policymakers to design carbon taxes perceived as fair.

91 Communicating that a redistribution decreases inequality in society in gen-
92 eral does not robustly affect citizens’ perceived fairness. Rather, policies
93 that minimise visible horizontal inequalities are more likely to be judged
94 as fair. At the same time, sociotropic concerns about inequality are filtered
95 through political ideology, suggesting that a one-size-fits-all fairness narrative
96 is unlikely to succeed. As the effects of inequality aversion are not sensitive
97 towards the sectoral scope of the tax, inequality aversion is primarily affected
98 by the actual distributional outcome.

99 **2. Theoretical Argument**

100 *2.1. Background*

101 Carbon taxation is widely regarded as an effective and efficient instru-
102 ment for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Sterner et al., 2019). Despite
103 its appeal, it has often encountered political resistance (Stadelmann-Steffen
104 and Dermont, 2018; Levi, 2021; Muhammad et al., 2021). This resistance
105 is largely explained in two ways: First, the higher the personal cost from a
106 carbon tax, the lower the support (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2018).
107 Second, a growing body of work shows that fairness perceptions are a cen-
108 tral driver of political support for such taxes (Schaffer, 2024; Kallbekken and
109 Sælen, 2011; Bergquist et al., 2022; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). Since car-
110 bon taxes create regressive outcomes, citizens voice concerns about fairness
111 (Farrell, 2017; Bergquist et al., 2022; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019).

112 To counter these concerns, governments rely on redistributing tax rev-
113 enue back to the population (Berry, 2019; Carl and Fedor, 2016). Such
114 redistributive schemes can render carbon taxation more progressive (Gevrek
115 and Uyduranoglu, 2015; Berry, 2019). In fact, studies have confirmed that
116 citizens prefer egalitarian or progressive redistributions that correct regres-
117 sive outcomes (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021; Beiser-McGrath and Bernauer,
118 2019). However, recent work showed that the effects of redistributions on
119 public acceptability are modest at best. They attributed null findings to low

120 saliency, limited know-how, or political moderation (Fremstad et al., 2022;
121 Mildenberger et al., 2022; Bürgisser et al., 2024).

122 This raises an important conceptual concern. If many citizens have only a
123 vague understanding of how revenues are redistributed (Mildenberger et al.,
124 2022), stated-preference elicitation for egalitarian or progressive redistribu-
125 tion might overestimate its effects. Individuals might endorse redistributive
126 schemes in principle, yet fail to perceive their distributive consequences. We
127 argue that it is therefore insufficient to study attitudes towards these re-
128 distributive schemes. What ultimately matters is how citizens perceive the
129 fairness of the distributional outcomes, once taxes paid and redistributions
130 received are considered jointly.

131 What drives perceived unfairness of distributional outcomes remains un-
132 derstudied in the context of carbon taxation (Sommer et al., 2022; Maestre-
133 Andrés et al., 2019). We follow recent work, which shows that people’s
134 perceptions of fairness are affected by both how policies affect them per-
135 sonally (egotropic concerns) and how they evaluate outcomes in relation to
136 others (sociotropic concerns) (Mansfield and Mutz, 2009; Beiser-McGrath
137 and Bernauer, 2024; Cavallé, 2023). Moreover, existing research largely ab-
138 stracts from the policy design of carbon taxation. We argue that distribu-
139 tional outcomes do not emerge in a vacuum: they are embedded in concrete
140 policy instruments that may cue different fairness norms and expectations.
141 Understanding fairness perceptions, therefore, requires not only analysing
142 who gains and who loses, but also how these gains and losses are generated
143 through specific tax-and-rebate designs (Bürgisser et al., 2024), especially
144 since what constitutes a fair outcome cannot be generalised (Alesina et al.,
145 2012; Fleurbaey and Maniquet, 2008).

146 We focus on the study of inequality aversion as a central mechanism
147 in explaining perceived fairness (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999). While inequality
148 aversion has been widely used to study behavioural and distributional prefer-
149 ences (Fischbacher et al., 2023; Engelmann and Strobel, 2004; Lü and Scheve,

150 2016), its integration into carbon tax design has been limited. Sommer et al.
151 (2022) highlight the potential of the Fehr-Schmidt framework to explain sup-
152 port for redistribution of carbon taxation, but do not test its influence empir-
153 ically. By directly presenting respondents with concrete post-redistributional
154 outcomes, we examine fairness perceptions under full information about who
155 gains and who loses. This shifts the focus from abstract preferences for re-
156 distributive schemes to the evaluation of tangible distributive outcomes.

157 This paper makes three contributions to the literature on carbon taxation
158 and fairness. First, we examine how inequality aversion shapes perceptions
159 of the fairness of distributional outcomes. While fairness has been identi-
160 fied as a key determinant of policy acceptability, fewer studies have analysed
161 how fairness perceptions form in response to realised tax-and-rebate out-
162 comes (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). By distinguishing between egotropic
163 and sociotropic inequality aversion, and further between advantaged and dis-
164 advantaged positions, we provide a fine-grained account of the behavioural
165 mechanisms through which individuals translate distributive inequalities into
166 fairness judgements. In doing so, we move beyond asking whether redistri-
167 bution increases acceptability and instead explain why certain distributive
168 outcomes are perceived as fair or unfair.

169 Second, we investigate how inequality aversion is politically conditioned.
170 Existing work shows that political orientation strongly structures attitudes
171 towards carbon taxation, often overriding material self-interest (Fremstad
172 et al., 2022). We extend this insight by examining whether the moral evalua-
173 tion of inequality itself is filtered through political orientation, thereby uncov-
174 ering how distributional outcomes can be interpreted differently depending
175 on normative beliefs. This helps to bridge behavioural models of inequal-
176 ity aversion with research on politicised climate policy debates (Heyen and
177 Wicki, 2024).

178 Third, we analyse whether the effects of inequality aversion are policy
179 dependent, that is, contingent on the object of taxation. Carbon tax policies

180 target heterogeneous domains of consumption — such as heating, transport
181 fuel, or air travel — which differ in visibility, perceived necessity, and associ-
182 ations with responsibility or luxury consumption (Büchs and Mattioli, 2024;
183 Bürgisser et al., 2024). Differentiating these tax objects allows us to test
184 whether fairness evaluations are stable across policy domains or are shaped
185 by sector-specific moral logics. By embedding distributive outcomes across
186 distinct policy contexts, we test whether fairness perceptions are not only
187 a function of who gains and who loses, but also of how carbon taxation is
188 designed.

189 *2.2. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses*

190 We assume that individuals are inequality averse (Fehr and Schmidt,
191 1999). In the context of carbon taxation, inequality may arise on the one
192 hand due to individual consumption patterns (Farrell, 2017) and on the other
193 hand through unequal redistributions of tax revenues back to the population
194 (Berry, 2019; Fremstad and Paul, 2019). We differentiate between egotropic
195 and sociotropic inequality aversion (Mansfield and Mutz, 2009). Egotropic
196 inequality aversion refers to concerns about one’s own relative position com-
197 pared to others (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999). Sociotropic inequality aversion
198 refers to concerns about inequality between social groups, independent of
199 one’s own position (Dimick et al., 2014). This distinction has recently been
200 explored as a predictor of carbon tax acceptability (Beiser-McGrath and
201 Bernauer, 2024; Schaffer, 2024). It remains unexplored, however, which aver-
202 sion drives the perception of fairness in the case of carbon taxation.

203 *Egotropic Inequality Aversion.* We build on the framework proposed in Fehr
204 and Schmidt (1999). Three dimensions cause disutility from unequal out-
205 comes: lower absolute payoffs, lower relative payoffs (disadvantaged inequal-
206 ity aversion, DIA), and higher relative payoffs (advantaged inequality aver-
207 sion, AIA). While the effects of DIA are based on feelings of envy, AIA is

208 associated with moral dissonance or guilt (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999; Fehr
209 et al., 2006; Lü and Scheve, 2016). We therefore expect:¹:

210 **Hypothesis 1 (H1):** *A negative expected monetary payoff decreases per-*
211 *ceived fairness of distributional outcomes.*

212 **Hypothesis 2 (H2):** *Disadvantaged inequality aversion decreases the per-*
213 *ceived fairness of distributional outcomes.*

214 **Hypothesis 3 (H3):** *Advantaged inequality aversion decreases the perceived*
215 *fairness of distributional outcomes.*

216 *Sociotropic Inequality Aversion.* Beyond self-centred considerations, individ-
217 uals may also care about inequality between social groups (Mansfield and
218 Mutz, 2009; Cavallé, 2023). Research has established that carbon taxes cre-
219 ate unfair outcomes due to their regressivity (Berry, 2019; Bergquist et al.,
220 2022). Sommer et al. (2022) show that perceived fairness of carbon pricing
221 depends on normative justice norms. Unequal distributional outcomes may
222 therefore be interpreted as violations of distributive justice, even by compara-
223 tively advantaged individuals. We therefore posit that sociotropic inequality
224 aversion (SIA) affects perceived fairness negatively:

225 **Hypothesis 4 (H4):** *Sociotropic inequality aversion decreases the perceived*
226 *fairness of distributional outcomes.*

227 While SIA is expected to reduce perceived fairness on average, its ef-
228 fect might not be uniform across individuals (Sommer et al., 2022). Carbon
229 taxation is a highly politicised policy in which distributive outcomes are in-
230 terpreted through normative and ideological lenses (Levi, 2021; Douenne and
231 Fabre, 2022; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). In particular, unequal outcomes
232 that disadvantage high-emitting households may be perceived as corrective or

¹See Appendix A.2 for a discussion of the pre-registered hypotheses.

233 deserved by some, while others may interpret them as unfair redistribution.
234 As a result, individuals may find some versions of inequality normatively
235 justified. Ideological perspectives might therefore moderate sociotropic in-
236 equality aversion. Prior research shows that political orientation strongly
237 shapes how citizens evaluate redistribution and climate policy (Fremstad
238 et al., 2022; Mildemberger et al., 2022). We test whether left-wing or right-
239 wing individuals behave differently towards unequal (sociotropic) outcomes.
240 In general, we assume that left-leaning respondents and those in favour of
241 carbon taxation react less to sociotropic inequality aversion when unequal
242 outcomes are to the detriment of high-emitting households in society (Thal-
243 mann, 2004). We do not expect political orientation to condition egotropic
244 inequality aversion, as self-relevant losses and gains are less susceptible to
245 ideological reinterpretation (Cavaillé, 2023).

246 **Hypothesis 5 (H5):** *The effects of sociotropic inequality aversion are at-*
247 *tenuated among left-leaning respondents when inequality is to the detriment*
248 *of high emitters.*

249 *Tax Object.* Finally, we test whether the effects of inequality aversion on per-
250 ceived fairness are policy-dependent. Specifically, unequal outcomes might
251 be judged differently depending on which objects (heating fuel tax, trans-
252 port fuel tax, air travel fee) the carbon tax is levied on. First, the Swiss
253 carbon tax is levied only on heating fuels, notably leaving out transport fuels
254 (Thalmann and Vielle, 2019). Citizens are accustomed to this tax object,
255 which can create potential policy learning and feedback effects on perceived
256 fairness (Carattini et al., 2019; Pierson, 1993). Air travel fees and transport
257 fuel taxes can thus be regarded as nascent policy options (Pierson, 1993).
258 However, since studies have pointed to a general lack of awareness of the car-
259 bon tax (Mildemberger et al., 2022; Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2018),
260 the learning hypothesis might not lead to different fairness evaluations. Sec-
261 ond, research has shown that transport fuel taxes are especially salient and

262 trigger distinct fairness concerns (Kallbekken and Aasen, 2010; Thalmann,
263 2004; Povitkina et al., 2021). A reason for this is the difference in the (per-
264 ceived) elasticities of demand of transport fuels (Sternner, 2007; Andersson,
265 2019; Landis et al., 2018). In the case of air travel, Bürgisser et al. (2024)
266 show that acceptability is generally higher for kerosene taxes than for other
267 tax objects. Since air travel taxes cause less regressive outcomes than energy
268 and motor fuel taxes (Büchs and Mattioli, 2024), there is also a potential dif-
269 ference in the perceived fairness, especially since egotropic considerations do
270 not seem to affect policy support for air travel taxes strongly (Larsson et al.,
271 2020). In sum, object-differentiated carbon taxes apply to heterogeneous
272 consumption patterns, thereby creating potential variations in how unequal
273 distributional outcomes are normatively justified.

274 **Hypothesis 6 (H6):** *The effects of inequality aversion on the perception of*
275 *fairness vary by tax object.*

276 3. Method

277 3.1. Factorial Survey Experiment

278 We conducted a within-subject factorial survey experiment (Auspurg and
279 Hinz, 2014). Factorial survey experiments have been successfully used in pre-
280 vious studies on fairness perceptions (Treischl and Wolbring, 2022). To im-
281 prove information equivalence, respondents were informed that the vignettes
282 were hypothetical and randomly constructed (Dafoe et al., 2018).

283 The vignettes showed distributional outcomes for two model households
284 presented in table form to enhance the salience of all attributes (Sauer et al.,
285 2020). We held household composition constant (two adults and two chil-
286 dren). They differed in income and energy consumption, whereas the higher-
287 income households always had higher consumption (Callahan, 2025). De-
288 pending on the tax object, the table showed that higher-income households
289 consumed more heating or transport fuel and travelled more by air than

300 for air travel were set at CHF 30 CHF, 75 and 120 per flight, reflecting pro-
301 posals in the rejected CO₂-law of 2021 (Federal Office for the Environment,
302 2021). The attribute *redistributive scheme* consisted of egalitarian, progres-
303 sive (higher rebate for lower-income households), or regressive (higher rebate
304 for higher-income households) levels. Since redistributions are an instrument
305 to combat regressivity (Berry, 2019), the choice of a regressive redistribution
306 scheme might appear hypothetical at first. However, regressive outcomes can
307 occur even with redistributions (Fremstad and Paul, 2019; Farrell, 2017), for
308 instance, when redistributive schemes are linked to prior emission-reducing
309 investments, such as building retrofits, which predominantly benefit richer
310 homeowners (Sommer et al., 2022; Infras, 2022). Importantly, our design
311 does not assume that respondents endorse this principle; rather, it allows
312 us to test how such distributional outcomes are perceived as fair or unfair,
313 regardless of the political or normative rationale behind them. The vignettes
314 were presented either in German or French. Respondents were informed that
315 part of the tax revenue would be redistributed to the population and part
316 would be used to promote renewable energy ("green earmarking"). By that,
317 we aimed to steer attention to the distributional effects and hold doubts
318 constant about the effectiveness of carbon taxation (Kallbekken and Aasen,
319 2010).

320 In order to estimate distributional outcomes, we relied on a simplified
321 revenue-neutral tax-and-rebate policy. First, the annual CO₂-levies were cal-
322 culated based on the shown consumption levels of each household multiplied
323 by the corresponding tax height level. Second, the annual redistribution
324 was based on calculations by (Siegrist et al., 2019). We assumed a con-
325 stant national emissions level, which we multiplied by the tax levy. This
326 resulted in a national tax revenue for each vignette. Similar to the current
327 Swiss carbon tax, we assumed that four-ninths of this total amount would
328 be redistributed back to the population (Federal Office for the Environment,
329 2020). The actual amount each model household received varied depend-

330 ing on the vignette’s redistribution scheme. Every household received the
331 same amount under the egalitarian redistributive scheme. In the progressive
332 scheme, the total amount redistributed was held constant. We assumed a
333 linearly decreasing function in which households with an annual income of
334 CHF 200,000 or more would receive no redistribution. In the regressive re-
335 distribution scheme, we inverted this function. Importantly, the attributes
336 of tax height and redistributive scheme were not shown in the vignette to di-
337 vert attention to the distributional outcomes and we wanted to decrease the
338 cognitive burden for respondents (Auspurg and Hinz, 2014). Although this
339 estimation approach clearly simplifies the real-world redistribution applied
340 in Switzerland and elsewhere (Federal Office for the Environment, 2020; Carl
341 and Fedor, 2016), it nonetheless provides experimental variability to study
342 the effects of unequal distributional outcomes. Although a carbon tax might
343 be levied at another point, we assumed the tax amount would be fully passed
344 on to the households.

345 Respondents were randomly assigned to one of five blocks, each containing
346 multiple vignettes. Each respondent was presented with five to six vignettes
347 of carbon tax policies, depending on the specific block, so that all of the
348 27 combinations were included in the factorial survey experiment. To avoid
349 order effects, the order of the vignettes within each block was randomised,
350 with a consistency vignette shown at the end of each block as a manipulation
351 check (Hauser et al., 2018; Kane and Barabas, 2019). Our outcome was the
352 perceived fairness of the resulting distributional outcome, measured on a
353 7-point Likert scale from very unfair to very fair.

354 To measure sociotropic inequality, we calculated the absolute differences
355 of net effects for the two model households in each vignette. For estimating
356 egotropic inequality, we estimated the net effect after redistributions for each
357 respondent and vignette by eliciting the following items: For carbon taxes
358 on heating fuels, the number of rooms in the respondent’s household was
359 multiplied by the mean room size to calculate the square footage (Federal

360 Statistical Office, 2023). This area was then multiplied by the assumed oil or
361 gas consumption per square foot (Federal Office for the Environment, 2022)
362 and by the vignette’s tax levy. For taxes on transport fuels, the estimated
363 distance travelled by car in a year was multiplied by the mean petrol or
364 diesel consumption per car. For air travel fees, the number of flights respon-
365 dents took per year was multiplied by the vignette’s tax levy. If the model
366 households in the vignettes had a lower net effect than what we estimated
367 respondents would receive, the difference was treated as an instance of ad-
368 vantaged inequality. On the contrary, if model households received more,
369 the difference was considered disadvantaged inequality for the respondents
370 (Lü and Scheve, 2016). To estimate the monetary payoff per respondent, we
371 asked respondents to rate their expected monetary effect on a 7-point Likert
372 scale (Very negative to very positive) for each of the three tax objects. The
373 variable was elicited after the vignettes to avoid pre-treating respondents.

374 3.2. Model

375 We regress the perceived fairness on the expected monetary payoff, the so-
376 ciotropic inequality aversion and the egotropic inequality aversion. Formally,
377 we analyse:

$$F_{i,j} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P_{i,j} + \beta_2 S_j + \beta_3 A_{i,j} + \beta_4 D_{i,j} + \gamma' \mathbf{X}_i + \epsilon_{i,j}$$

378 The perceived fairness F per individual i and tax alternative (vignette)
379 j is regressed on the expected monetary payoff P , the (alternative specific)
380 sociotropic inequality S and egotropic inequality (advantaged inequality aver-
381 sion A and disadvantaged inequality aversion D). We z-standardise measures
382 of sociotropic and egotropic inequality to facilitate better comparisons. X is
383 a vector of controls. We control for binary gender. Age is treated as a nu-
384 meric variable, even though we elicited the variable on a discrete scale in the
385 survey. We include language in our estimation strategy (French or German).
386 Next, we divide household income by the square root of household size to ob-

387 tain an equivalence income measure. Lastly, we control for the urbanisation
388 rate of the respondents' addresses.

389 We provide the relevant survey items in the appendix (Appendix A.4).

390 *3.3. Data*

391 We use an original dataset specifically collected for this analysis. We ob-
392 tained the addresses of 4,226 Swiss citizens from the Swiss Federal Statistical
393 Office's sampling frame. Their sampling frame includes a comprehensive list
394 of all registered individuals in Switzerland. Each individual in the sample
395 received a postal letter detailing the study, along with a unique token to
396 access the online survey. The survey was conducted between January 8 and
397 March 11, 2024, with one postal reminder sent in February to encourage
398 participation. Participation was incentivised with a lottery.

399 We base our approach on Switzerland. The country offers a unique case
400 study, given its direct democracy and the population's familiarity with car-
401 bon taxation mechanisms (Schaffer, 2024). Since 2008, Switzerland has im-
402 plemented a carbon tax on heating fuel (Federal Office for the Environment,
403 2020). However, Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont (2018) have shown that
404 a majority of Swiss citizens are unaware of the carbon tax system in place,
405 which allows testing underlying mechanisms without policy feedback bias
406 (Pierson, 1993). Given sectoral differentiation, we can practically investigate
407 whether perceptions of fairness differ across policy sectors.

408 A total of 770 respondents (18%) completed the survey. We deleted obser-
409 vations with missing values, resulting in a final dataset of 4,032 observations.
410 The sample is well-balanced across age cohorts and gender (see table A.4).
411 There is an over-representation of higher-educated people (with secondary
412 or tertiary education) compared to the overall Swiss population, as well as
413 an under-representation of low-income households (Federal Statistical Office,
414 2022). German-speaking individuals are also slightly over-represented in the
415 sample. We control for these potential selection biases.

416 The response rate is slightly lower than that in other studies that invite
417 a random sample to participate in experimental surveys (Epper et al., 2024).
418 Table 1 reports summary statistics of our final dataset.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variable	N	Min	Mean	Median	SD	Max
Perceived Fairness	4032	1	4.38	4	1.61	7
Expected Payoff (1: Very negative, 7: Very positive)	3194	1	3.91	4	1.95	7
Advantaged Inequality Aversion (CHF)	4032	100	1212	900	1064	4300
Disadvantaged Inequality Aversion (CHF)	4032	0	948	602	965	5990
Sociotropic Inequality Aversion (CHF)	4032	0	131	0	310	2862
Carbon Tax Object	4032					
... Heating fuel	1507	37.4%				
... Transport fuel	1067	26.5%				
... Air travel	1458	36.2%				
Trust in Politicians (1: Distrust, 7: Trust)	4011	1	4.86	5	1.4	7
Belief in Effectiveness (1: Sceptics, 7: Believers)	3942	1	4.73	5	1.55	7
Political Attitude (1: Left-wing, 5: Centre, 9: Right-wing)	3820	1	4.87	5	1.87	9
Gender	4032					
... Female	1930	47.9%				
... Male	2090	51.8%				
... Non-binary	12	0.3%				
Age	4032					
... 18-35	717	17.8%				
... 36-65	2160	53.6%				
... Above 65	991	24.6%				
... No Answer	164	4.1%				
Annual Squared Equivalence Household Income (CHF)	3868	13416	63454	61500	23192	150012
Language	4032					
... French	724	18%				
... German	3308	82%				
Urbanisation Rate (Percentage)	4001	0.00826	0.289	0.253	0.193	0.942

419 4. Results

420 4.1. Inequality Aversion

421 In table 2, we report our regression results. For all regressions, we con-
422 trol for trust in politicians and belief in the effectiveness of carbon taxes,
423 as these variables influence how individuals generally perceive carbon taxes
424 (Bergquist et al., 2022; Levi, 2021; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021; Fairbrother
425 et al., 2019). Moreover, we control for (binary) gender, age, squared equiv-
426 alence household income, language, and the urbanisation rate of the living

427 area. All standard errors are corrected for heteroscedasticity. The measures
428 of inequality aversion are z-standardised to facilitate better comparisons.
429 Column 1 reports regression results, where we regressed perceived fairness
430 on the egotropic inequality aversion measures. Column 2 presents regres-
431 sion results in which we regress perceived fairness on sociotropic inequality
432 aversion. The full model with sociotropic and egotropic inequality aversion
433 measures is shown in column 3.

434 As expected, an increase in the expected monetary payoff increases the
435 perceived fairness of the carbon tax (H1). An increase of 1 unit in expected
436 payoff raises perceived fairness in the model by 0.17 units ($p < 0.001$). Ad-
437 vantaged inequality aversion reduces perceived fairness by 0.25 to 0.28 units
438 ($p < 0.001$). We confirm H3. The effect of disadvantaged inequality aversion
439 is smaller (-0.06 to -0.09, $p < 0.05$). Nonetheless, we accept H2.

440 We find that sociotropic inequality aversion reduces perceived fairness
441 (H4) in column 2 (-0.07, $p < 0.01$). In the full model (column 3), significance
442 and hypothesised direction are lost. Thus, H4 is only accepted when there is
443 no evaluation from an egotropic perspective (Beiser-McGrath and Bernauer,
444 2024).

445 *4.2. Moderation by Political Orientation*

446 In figure 2, we calculate marginal effects by political orientation. Re-
447 spondents are considered right-leaning if they scored between 6 and 9 on a
448 9-point Likert scale. Conversely, left-leaning respondents scored between 1
449 and 3. In our sample, 48% of respondents are considered politically centrist.
450 25% are left-wing and 22% right-wing. To obtain marginal effects, every
451 other variable of the full model is held at the mean or median (see table 1).

452 We observe a clear interaction effect: increasing sociotropic inequality
453 aversion is associated with political orientation. The positive association be-
454 tween sociotropic inequality aversion and perceived fairness is evident only
455 among left-leaning respondents. Among right-leaning individuals, higher lev-
456 els of sociotropic inequality are associated with a significant decrease in per-

	EIA	SIA	Full Model
Expected Payoff	0.17*** (0.01)		0.17*** (0.01)
Advantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.25*** (0.03)		-0.28*** (0.03)
Disadvantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.06* (0.03)		-0.09** (0.03)
Sociotropic Inequality Aversion		-0.07** (0.02)	0.06 (0.03)
Trust in Politicians	0.02 (0.02)	0.05** (0.02)	0.02 (0.02)
Belief in Carbon Tax Effectiveness	0.42*** (0.02)	0.41*** (0.02)	0.42*** (0.02)
Female	0.05 (0.05)	0.01 (0.05)	0.05 (0.05)
Age	0.08*** (0.02)	0.04 (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)
Squared Equivalence Income	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
French-speaking	-0.44*** (0.07)	-0.49*** (0.06)	-0.45*** (0.07)
Urbanisation Rate	0.03 (0.13)	0.17 (0.13)	0.01 (0.13)
Intercept	1.36*** (0.16)	2.04*** (0.14)	1.37*** (0.16)
R ²	0.27	0.19	0.28
Adj. R ²	0.27	0.19	0.27
Num. obs.	2977	3721	2977

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

Legend: EIA = Egotropic Inequality Aversion, SIA = Sociotropic Inequality Aversion.
Note: Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. The sociotropic inequality aversion, advantaged inequality aversion and disadvantaged inequality aversion are z-standardised.

Table 2: Inequality Aversion on Perceived Fairness

457 ceived fairness. These results reinforce the argument that fairness perceptions
458 must be understood through a political lens (Alesina et al., 2012; Cavallé,
459 2023), and political attitudes influence how citizens evaluate the distribu-
460 tional outcomes of carbon taxes in general (Fremstad et al., 2022). See table
461 A.5 in the appendix with full regression results.

462 *4.3. Differences by Tax Object*

463 Next, we test whether respondents differ in how they evaluate the distri-
464 butional outcomes of different tax objects. Overall, the results are not tax-
465 object-dependent. There are minor differences regarding significance. Figure
466 3 reports point estimates and heteroskedastic-robust 95% confidence inter-
467 vals. For all objects, the expected monetary payoff significantly increases
468 perceived fairness. We detect the expected negative effect of advantaged
469 inequality aversion for all three tax objects. Disadvantaged inequality aver-
470 sion loses its significance when differentiating by tax object. We attribute
471 non-significance primarily to the low sample size.

472 The differentiation shows that the positive effect of sociotropic inequality
473 aversion in the full model is primarily driven by air travel fees. The positive
474 preference indicates that respondents prefer stronger sociotropic inequality
475 (i.e., a larger difference in household outcomes), since air travel fees are re-
476 garded as more regressive without redistribution (Büchs and Mattioli, 2024).
477 Table A.6 contains the full regression results. H6 is nonetheless rejected: For
478 all investigated tax objects, the effects of inequality aversion are similar in
479 direction and significance.

480 *4.4. Robustness*

481 We test the robustness of these findings with several strategies. Table
482 3 shows regression results for our robustness checks. Overall, the results
483 confirm the stability of the original model’s findings.

484 In column 1, we subset the used data based on respondents’ confidence in
485 answering the factorial survey experiment. Immediately after the vignettes,

Figure 2: Marginal effects of increasing sociotropic inequality moderated by political orientation on perceived fairness. All other variables are held constant at their means or medians.

Figure 3: Regression results of inequality aversion measures differentiated by tax objects

	Confident	Consistent	Weighted	Post-Stratified	Binary
Expected Payoff	0.19*** (0.02)	0.20*** (0.02)	0.21*** (0.03)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.21*** (0.02)
Advantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.31*** (0.04)	-0.28*** (0.04)	-0.19** (0.06)	-0.27*** (0.03)	-0.39*** (0.06)
Disadvantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.09* (0.04)	-0.13*** (0.04)	-0.10* (0.04)	-0.09** (0.03)	-0.11* (0.05)
Sociotropic Inequality Aversion	0.05 (0.04)	0.07 (0.04)	-0.09 (0.06)	0.05 (0.03)	0.12* (0.05)
Trust in Politicians	0.01 (0.03)	0.04 (0.02)	0.03 (0.03)	0.02 (0.03)	0.07* (0.03)
Belief in Carbon Tax Effectiveness	0.48*** (0.02)	0.46*** (0.02)	0.39*** (0.03)	0.43*** (0.03)	0.47*** (0.03)
Female	0.08 (0.07)	-0.04 (0.07)	0.08 (0.10)	0.03 (0.08)	-0.05 (0.08)
Age	0.04 (0.03)	0.09** (0.03)	0.05 (0.04)	0.07* (0.03)	0.07 (0.04)
Squared Equivalence Income	-0.00* (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00* (0.00)
French-speaking	-0.41*** (0.10)	-0.80*** (0.09)	-0.45*** (0.12)	-0.44*** (0.11)	-0.42*** (0.11)
Urbanisation Rate	0.32 (0.17)	-0.31 (0.17)	-0.28 (0.28)	0.02 (0.21)	0.38 (0.22)
Intercept	1.50*** (0.22)	1.19*** (0.20)	1.38*** (0.26)	1.39*** (0.26)	-3.79*** (0.28)
R ²	0.31	0.36	0.29		
Adj. R ²	0.31	0.36	0.29		
Num. obs.	1805	1691	2970	2977	2977
Deviance				5446.79	3569.96
Dispersion				1.83	
AIC					3593.96
BIC					3665.95
Log Likelihood					-1784.98

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Note: The variables for sociotropic, advantaged and disadvantaged inequality aversion were z-standardized. Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses.

Table 3: Robustness Check

486 respondents indicated their confidence in their answers on a scale from 1
487 (Very hard) to 7 (Very easy). 425 of 770 respondents indicated that the
488 questions were (rather) easy to answer(55%). In column 2, we subset for
489 consistent respondents. We included a manipulation check at the end of the
490 factorial survey experiment (Hauser et al., 2018; Kane and Barabas, 2019).
491 Respondents responded twice to the same vignette. 56% of our respondents
492 were consistent in their answers (n = 428). In column 3, we weighted the
493 full model to check if our results are driven by an environmentally friendly
494 bias in our sample. Out of 770 respondents, 67% indicated to be (rather) in
495 favour of carbon taxation (n = 514). However, in a 2021 popular vote, only
496 49% of voters favoured new carbon taxation (Swiss Federal Council, 2021).
497 We use these ratios to weight our initial regression approach. In column 4,
498 we analyse a potential non-response bias by conducting a post-stratification
499 analysis using survey weights. Respondent-level weights were constructed
500 to match population margins for the Swiss adult population by age group,
501 gender, and language region, since these are the variables we have available
502 for all respondents in our sample. In column 5, we split the response vari-
503 able into Fair/Not fair and rerun a logistic regression to compare the effect
504 size and coefficients. Out of 4,032 vignettes, 50% were rated as (rather) fair
505 (n = 1,997). Across all specifications, the expected monetary payoff consis-
506 tently shows a strong, positive, and highly significant effect on the perceived
507 fairness. Advantaged inequality aversion retains a significant negative effect
508 throughout, although its size and significance slightly decrease in the third
509 robustness specification. Disadvantage aversion is more pronounced, espe-
510 cially among consistent respondents. Sociotropic inequality aversion, which
511 was not significant in the original full model, is significant in the logistic re-
512 gression. We do not interpret this as a conclusive finding. Other covariates,
513 such as belief in the effectiveness of carbon taxes and being French-speaking,
514 remain robust predictors, while age and income effects show minor variation.
515 Overall, the results support the main model and suggest that the effects are

516 not sensitive to respondent confidence or consistency, a biased sample, or the
517 functional form of the dependent variable.

518 **5. Discussion**

519 This paper examines how inequality aversion shapes perceptions of fair-
520 ness regarding the distributional outcomes of a carbon tax. The results point
521 towards three substantive insights.

522 Firstly, our findings suggest that fairness perceptions of carbon taxation
523 are anchored less in abstract support for redistributive schemes and more in
524 relational self-positioning within the final distribution of outcomes (Beiser-
525 McGrath and Bernauer, 2024). While much of the literature focuses on how
526 carbon tax revenues should be redistributed to achieve a fair, i.e., progressive,
527 outcome (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019), our results indicate that individuals
528 evaluate fairness primarily through comparisons between their own net po-
529 sition and salient reference points. In particular, aversion to advantageous
530 unequal outcomes emerges as the most robust predictor of perceived unfair-
531 ness. This aligns with other findings, which posit that individuals experience
532 moral discomfort when benefiting disproportionately from unequal outcomes,
533 not only resentment when they lose out (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999). Fairness
534 perceptions are not reducible to material self-interest alone, nor to princi-
535 pled commitments to progressivity in society as a whole. This mechanism
536 helps explain why tax-and-rebate policies that are progressive on average may
537 nevertheless encounter resistance, even among groups that benefit financially
538 (Fremstad et al., 2022; Mildemberger et al., 2022). Aggregate progressivity
539 does not necessarily translate into perceived fairness when visible disparities
540 in net outcomes remain salient.

541 Secondly, the analysis further demonstrates that sociotropic inequality
542 does not operate as a universally shared fairness heuristic (Alesina et al.,
543 2012). Instead, its effect depends strongly on political orientation. We find
544 that inequality to the detriment of high emitters is acceptable among left-

545 leaning respondents, whereas right-leaning respondents generally react neg-
546 atively to greater disparities after redistribution. This pattern indicates that
547 distributive outcomes are filtered through ideological frameworks, rather than
548 being evaluated according to a politically neutral equality norm (Jagers et al.,
549 2021; Povitkina et al., 2021). Fairness in the context of carbon taxation is
550 therefore not a stable moral constant but a contested interpretative lens,
551 which mirrors findings from research on acceptability (Bürgisser et al., 2024;
552 Fremstad et al., 2022). This suggests that appeals to reducing inequality do
553 not operate as universally shared fairness cues. Distributional narratives are
554 filtered through ideological frameworks and may generate divergent reactions
555 depending on political orientation.

556 Thirdly, contrary to our expectations, the policy design of carbon taxation
557 does not substantially alter the relationship between inequality aversion and
558 fairness perceptions. Although heating fuel, transport fuel, and air travel
559 differ in visibility, necessity, and perceived luxury status (Büchs and Mattioli,
560 2024; Bürgisser et al., 2024), respondents apply similar distributive heuristics
561 once distributional outcomes are made explicit. This suggests that fairness
562 evaluations are driven more by the perceived structure of gains and losses
563 than by the specific policy design.

564 Our paper has several limitations: While the factorial survey design pro-
565 vides internal validity of causal claims by systematically varying distribu-
566 tional outcomes under controlled conditions, the external validity of our
567 findings warrants careful consideration (Auspurg and Hinz, 2014). The low
568 response rate increases the risk of self-selection, particularly among respon-
569 dents with higher levels of education or stronger prior interest in climate
570 policy. Although we address observable imbalances through weighting and
571 post-stratification, unobserved differences cannot be ruled out. Moreover,
572 the study is conducted solely in Switzerland, a country with an established
573 carbon tax and distinctive institutional features (Schaffer, 2024). These con-
574 textual characteristics may shape baseline familiarity with carbon taxation

575 and distributive debates (Carattini et al., 2025). Replication in other po-
576 litical and institutional settings is necessary to assess the generalisability of
577 the relational fairness mechanisms identified here. Finally, respondents eval-
578 uated hypothetical but information-rich scenarios. Although this enhances
579 clarity regarding distributive outcomes, real-world policy debates may in-
580 volve lower levels of information, strategic framing, and greater emotional
581 mobilisation, which could amplify or attenuate inequality-based fairness con-
582 cerns (Bürgisser et al., 2024; Fremstad et al., 2022). We also want to stress
583 that the policy design variation shown in our vignette could have been easily
584 overlooked, thereby decreasing the object-specific differences in results.

585 **6. Conclusion**

586 Our results contribute to broader debates on distributive justice and the
587 governance of sustainability transitions (Dolšak and Prakash, 2022; Jenk-
588 ins et al., 2016). Carbon taxation is frequently defended as economically
589 efficient, yet its durability depends on whether citizens perceive its distribu-
590 tional consequences as fair (Bergquist et al., 2022). Our findings suggest that
591 legitimacy cannot be secured through aggregate progressivity alone (Maestre-
592 Andrés et al., 2019). Fairness perceptions are shaped by relative positioning
593 and ideological interpretation, indicating that climate policy operates within
594 a politically contested moral landscape (Mildenberger et al., 2022)

595 These findings offer empirical grounding for the principle of “leaving no
596 one behind,” which increasingly guides the expansion of carbon taxation into
597 consumer-oriented sectors (Pahle, 2023). Our results suggest that this prin-
598 ciple resonates because fairness perceptions are highly sensitive to visible
599 disparities in net outcomes. Citizens evaluate carbon taxation not only in
600 terms of aggregate progressivity, but through relational comparisons that
601 highlight who gains and who loses. Operationalising “leaving no one behind”,
602 therefore, requires designing policies that minimise salient inequalities in out-
603 comes and make compensation mechanisms transparent and credible. In this

604 sense, the principle is not merely normatively appealing but aligned with
605 how individuals form fairness judgements in practice.

606 For policymakers, the implication is therefore not merely to design pro-
607 gressive schemes, but to anticipate how distributional differences are per-
608 ceived. Fairness concerns revolve less around who benefits most and more
609 around how unequal the final allocation appears to be. Attending to these
610 relational dynamics may prove decisive for sustaining political support as
611 carbon pricing expands into politically sensitive sectors.

612 **Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing**

613 During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT-5.2 and
614 LanguageTool to improve the language. After using these tools, the authors
615 reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for
616 the publication's content.

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627 The survey used in the paper received human subject review clearance
628 from the Human Subjects Committee of the University of Lucerne. The
629 survey used in this paper was registered with AsPredicted in December 2023
630 (No. 154118).

631 **Author contributions**

632 **Oliver Prinzing:** Conceptualisation, Data curation, Formal analysis,
633 Methodology, Visualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review &
634 editing. **Andreas Balthasar:** Funding acquisition, Project administration,
635 Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Aline Hänggli:** Validation, Writ-
636 ing – review & editing. **Amadea Tschannen:** Project administration, Su-
637 pervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

638 **Data statement**

639 Data and replication material can be made available upon request.

640 **Appendix A. Appendix**

641 *Appendix A.1. Sample Statistics*

	Sample	Relative	Population
Age: 18-35	141	0.18	0.27
Age: 36-65	415	0.54	0.51
Age: Above 65	182	0.24	0.22
Age: No Answer	32	0.04	*
Education: Primary	26	0.03	0.17
Education: Secondary	278	0.36	0.41
Education: Tertiary	452	0.59	0.42
Education: No Answer	14	0.02	*
Gender: Female	384	0.50	0.51
Gender: Male	383	0.50	0.49
Gender: Non-binary	3	0.00	*
Household Income (CHF): Below 4,000	81	0.11	0.4
Household Income (CHF): 4,001-7,000	226	0.29	0.2
Household Income (CHF): 7,001-11,000	238	0.31	0.2
Household Income (CHF): Above 11,001	166	0.22	0.2
Household Income (CHF): No Answer	59	0.08	*
Language: French	148	0.19	0.27
Language: German	622	0.81	0.73

Table A.4: Descriptive Statistics of Sample

642 *Appendix A.2. Pre-registered Hypotheses*

643 The survey used in this paper was registered with AsPredicted in Decem-
 644 ber 2023 (No. 154118). We registered the following hypotheses:

- 645 1. Where the tax is levied (heating, transport, or kerosene) affects how
 646 people perceive distributional outcomes.
- 647 2. The higher the tax levied, the lower the perceived fairness of the out-
 648 come.
- 649 3. People generally perceive lump-sum dividends as fairer as rebates tar-
 650 getted to specific parts of the population.

651 4. Disadvantaged inequality aversion will have a bigger effect on the per-
652 ceived fairness than advantaged equality aversion

653 We discarded the analysis of hypotheses 2 and 3 during the study because
654 we felt the effects had been extensively demonstrated elsewhere (Maestre-
655 Andrés et al., 2019; Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2018). Instead, we
656 modified hypotheses 4 into three hypotheses (H1, H3, H2). This allowed us
657 to stay closer to the original Fehr-Schmidt framework, while not omitting the
658 research interest in the pre-registration (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999). We did not
659 pre-register H4 and H5 and regard them as explorative in that regard. This
660 research interest sprang up while working on this paper (Beiser-McGrath
661 and Bernauer, 2024; Schaffer, 2024). However, we feel that including this
662 hypothesis does not violate the idea of pre-registration and actually includes a
663 more salient variable from our survey than the egotropic inequality measures.
664 In our view, the inclusion helps the readability and scope of this study.

665 *Appendix A.3. Regression Tables*

	Full Sample	Interaction
Expected Payoff	0.17*** (0.01)	0.16*** (0.01)
AIA	-0.28*** (0.03)	-0.28*** (0.03)
DIA	-0.09** (0.03)	-0.09** (0.03)
SIA	0.06 (0.03)	0.21*** (0.05)
Political Orientation: Centre		0.05 (0.06)
Political Orientation: Right		-0.37*** (0.08)
Interaction: SIA x Centre		-0.16** (0.06)
Interaction: SIA x Right		-0.35*** (0.07)
Trust in Politicians	0.02 (0.02)	0.03 (0.02)
Belief in Carbon Tax Effectiveness	0.42*** (0.02)	0.40*** (0.02)
Female	0.05 (0.05)	-0.01 (0.05)
Age	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)
Squared Equivalence Income	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
French-speaking	-0.45*** (0.07)	-0.49*** (0.08)
Urbanisation Rate	0.01 (0.13)	-0.05 (0.13)
Intercept	1.37*** (0.16)	1.57*** (0.18)
R ²	0.28	0.30
Adj. R ²	0.27	0.29
Num. obs.	2977	2855

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

Legend: EIA = Egotropic Inequality Aversion, SIA = Sociotropic Inequality Aversion.

Note: The variables for sociotropic, advantaged and disadvantaged inequality aversion were z-standardized. Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses.

Table A.5: Moderated Effects by Political Orientation

	Full Inequality Aversion	Heating Fuel Tax	Transport Fuel Tax	Air Travel Fee
Sociotropic Inequality Aversion	0.06 (0.03)	0.09 (0.09)	0.08 (0.05)	0.25* (0.11)
Expected Payoff	0.17*** (0.01)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.20*** (0.03)	0.15*** (0.02)
Advantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.28*** (0.03)	-0.35** (0.13)	-0.24*** (0.05)	-0.32*** (0.04)
Disadvantaged Inequality Aversion	-0.09** (0.03)	-0.08 (0.05)	-0.11 (0.07)	-0.25* (0.12)
Female	0.05 (0.05)	0.07 (0.08)	-0.00 (0.10)	0.06 (0.09)
Age	0.08*** (0.02)	0.12*** (0.04)	0.06 (0.04)	0.06 (0.04)
Squared Equivalence Income	0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	0.00* (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)
French-speaking	-0.45*** (0.07)	-0.43*** (0.12)	-0.38** (0.14)	-0.52*** (0.12)
Urbanisation Rate	0.01 (0.13)	0.45* (0.21)	-0.11 (0.27)	-0.40 (0.21)
Intercept	1.37*** (0.16)	1.17*** (0.26)	1.39*** (0.31)	1.62*** (0.27)
R ²	0.28	0.27	0.27	0.29
Adj. R ²	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.28
Num. obs.	2977	1104	810	1063

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$
Note: Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. The sociotropic inequality aversion, advantaged inequality aversion and disadvantaged inequality aversion are z-standardised.

Table A.6: Differentiation by Tax Object

No.	Item	Question	Measure
1	Trust in Politicians	I trust the work of the Swiss federal council.	7-point Likert scale
2	Left-Right scale	Where do you place yourself from Left to Right?	9-point Likert scale
3	Belief in Effectiveness	A carbon tax leads to more environmentally products being bought.	7-point Likert scale
4	Gender	What gender are you?	Categorical (1-3)
5	Age	How old are you?	Ordinal (1-6)
6	Education	What is your highest achieved education?	Ordinal (1-6)
7	Household Income	How high is the net income of your entire household?	Ordinal (1-8)
8	Household Size	How many persons (children included) live in your household?	Numeric
9	Expected Monetary Payoff	Which financial consequences would you expect from a carbon tax on heating fuel/transport fuel/fee on air travel	7-point Likert scale

Table A.7: Survey Items

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